

English Philology Language Teaching

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Learning approaches: the role of computer training programs in self-study

Abstract: Nowadays one of the most crucial issues of education is to introduce the latest technologies to students and use them efficiently. This article aims to provide detailed information about methodology of computer training programs to English Language learners.

Keywords: software, price, length, PC.

Introduction

Since the computer was invented, every branch of people's lives has completely changed. Now we should pay attention to education field. Computer assisted language learning has come to a new step, especially with the development of microcomputer and the Internet. Computers with their the best programs can facilitate a variety of learning tasks and have enormous potency as teaching tools.

There are a number of special programs available. Connecting with the progressive development of society, there has been an extremely huge interest to learn a foreign language. Because travelling the world, discovering the world, a desire to know about other cultures can be a great motivation. Without knowledge no one can do that.

There are a few English learning software programs people can buy and learn by them. These programs are a great way to add a little extra help and structure (organization) to your learning. Most learning software programs use different methods of teaching.

When you're choosing an English learning program, these are some of the things you should consider:

- Price.** How expensive is the program? Does it take monthly payments, one single payment or do you have to buy different levels separately?
- English level.** If you are a beginner, you will need to start in the low levels. If you're more advanced, you might not need the beginner levels.
- Length.** How long do you plan to spend on this program every day? Look at the length of each lesson and see if it will suit your lifestyle and the way you study.
- Availability.** Some of these programs need you to download software. Others just need you to have an Internet connection. A few, like Rosetta Stone and Pimsleur, can even be found in many libraries for you to check out and use for free. Decide how you prefer to use your program and it will help you figure out which one to use.

Here are some effective programs for anyone who wants to learn quickly:

1.Learn Speak English

Description: Learn Speak English is an application provided by Microsoft. It will work both on your Android mobile device as well as your PC computer. The Learn Speak English application will help you with your English pronunciation.

2.FluentU

Description: FluentU is a language learning program that teaches English through bite-sized authentic videos (real native videos, the kind native speakers actually watch). You can use it in your browser as well as on your phone as a downloadable app for iOS and Android devices.

3.Hello English

Description: Like Learn Speak English, you can download Hello English from Microsoft. The application is available for your Android mobile device and your PC computer. Hello English is used by millions of English learners to master English speaking. This is another free application that's a good introduction to English learning software.

4.Rosetta Stone

Description: Rosetta Stone is a popular program that has been around for many years. It allows you to learn English on your own schedule and on various devices. The program focuses on building vocabulary with interactive lessons.

5.Instant Immersion

Description: Instant Immersion is another program that builds your language skills with interactive exercises. While it's available as computer software, you can transfer lessons to your mobile device. You also get an interactive DVD.

6.Living Language

Description: With downloadable software or a subscription program, Living Language provides English learners with three levels of learning, from "essential" English to advanced English. You can also choose from specialty courses such as business, travel and career-specific (law enforcement, health, education) English.

7.Rocket Languages

Description: Rocket Languages was started in 2004 by two friends. The program is designed to have users speaking from the first lesson and reduce study time. You can use lessons across a variety of devices.

8.Duolingo

Description: Duolingo understands that learning a language can be expensive. They've created a program that will teach you the same information you would learn in a semester of a university-level language course, but in an interactive way, and for free.

9. Bubbles

Description: Bubbles is a software that emphasizes teacher-learner participation. In contrast to other software programs, Bubbles is conceived as an aid to developing spoken communication skills between participants using the software.

10. Tell Me More Kids Ingles

Description: A fun and immersive software package that helps children learn English while exploring an extremely well-designed virtual environment. Tell me More provides a wide variety of learning games and activities including Karaoke. This package is especially designed for Spanish speaking children, but other packages in other languages are available as well.

11. Curious George Learns Phonics

Description: Learning to read by the use of phonics has proved time and again to be one of the best approaches to getting kids to read. While this product is not specifically designed for ESL students, it is perfect for improving and expanding vocabulary for students who have reached an intermediate stage.

Conclusion

Using computer programs in language learning transforms students from passive recipients to active learners and allows more profound and enriching linguistic immersion. As you can see, there are plenty of fun, affordable ways to learn English right on your PC.

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